

YOGA EDUCATION FOR A HEALTHY WAY OF LIFE

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Abstract

Yoga has a diverse range of things that it can offer. It could be said that a primary goal of yoga is to gain balance and control in one's life. To provide a sense of calm that comes from the practice of yogic exercises and the practice of breath control and also to provide independence and freedom from confusion and distress in one's own personal life as well as in social life. Yoga teaches you that, when there is a perfect harmony between mind and body, we achieve total balance and control. Yoga education could help to equip oneself with basic knowledge about one's personality, to learn to handle oneself well in all life situations, to learn techniques of gaining good health, to develop a discriminative mind capable of knowing the real from the unreal and to face the dualities of life with equanimity. Yoga education can enhance all the activities of the students, be it academic or sport or social. Yoga techniques provide improved attention in studies, better stamina and co-ordination for sports and a heightened awareness and balanced attitude for social activity. Yoga is a way to learn and understand the spiritual India. Also, yoga is associated with the culture and heritage of India. In Sanskrit, yoga means 'to unite' and describes a way to live a healthy life. In yoga, the mind is disciplined through meditation and the body is aligned and strengthened. As per yoga, it is actually the nervous system of the body that affects our health. The nervous system gets purified with daily yoga and thus keeps our body healthy and strong. The origin of yoga is considered to be as old as human civilization. But there is no strong evidence to prove this statement. In spite of extensive research in this field, there are no concrete findings regarding the origin of yoga. Yoga exercises have a strengthening effect on the nervous system through its non-tiring physiological activities that bring about poise of body and mind. Unlike the normal workouts that concentrate more on the inflation of the muscles, Yoga takes care of every little part of the anatomy. This paper discusses the role of yoga education for a health way of life.

Key Words: Yoga, Education, Asanas.

Introduction

“Yoga is the control of thoughts- waves in the mind

Water flows continually into the ocean

But the ocean is never disturbed.

Desire flows into the mind of the seer

But he never disturbed

The seer knows peace...

He knows peace who has forgotten desire

Free from ego, free from pride.”

Bhagavad Gita

The origin of yoga is considered to be as old as human civilization. But there is no strong evidence to prove this statement. In spite of extensive research in this field, there are no concrete findings regarding the origin of yoga. It is believed that yoga originated in India about 5,000 years ago. Many Western scholars earlier used to believe that it was not 5,000 years ago but in the period of the Buddha (around 500 B.C) when yoga came into existence. During the excavation of the earliest known civilization of Indus Valley, very astonishing facts came forward. The soapstone seals that existed during that period have been found engraved with figures resembling that of a yogi sitting in a yoga-like posture. Originally, yoga started for the betterment of a community rather than the self.

Yoga is an all-embracing way of life, a science of self-culture and mental discipline that ensures the purgation of the ignoble in man and brings forth what is most noble in him. It is pertinent to all people irrespective of his caste, creed, sex, and religion. It can be beneficial to all - the good and the bad, the sick and the healthy, the believer and the non-believer, the literate and the ignorant, the young and the old. A person may begin at any age and can go on reaping its benefits. There are number of meanings in use of the word Yoga such as union, fortune, contribution, meeting, relationship, meditation, addition, etc;

- It is defined as the “Training of consciousness for a state of perfect spiritual insight and tranquility that is achieved through the three paths of actions and knowledge and devotion”.
- Can help man, to transform man’s life in to what is should be enrichment with truth.
- Yoga is often described as skilling action.

- Yoga is best curative and preventive medicine for most of the ills of mans resulting from the so called modern living.
- Yoga is described as a state of separation from sorrow.

Yoga Education Salient features are

- Yoga is a way of life. Yoga can be defined as Science of Health, Harmony and Happiness. Purely in theoretical sense yoga is the Science and art of realizing The Absolute i.e. The Ultimate Reality or Supreme Consciousness
- Yoga education aims to impart Yoga teaching in a pattern which may be termed as Holistic Living i.e.
 - ✓ Physical,
 - ✓ Mental,
 - ✓ Emotional,
 - ✓ Intellectual,
 - ✓ Social and
 - ✓ Spiritual well being

Yoga is a way to learn and understand the spiritual India. Also, yoga is associated with the culture and heritage of India. In Sanskrit, yoga means ‘to unite’ and describes a way to live a healthy life. In yoga, the mind is disciplined through meditation and the body is aligned and strengthened. As per yoga, it is actually the nervous system of the body that affects our health. The nervous system gets purified with daily yoga and thus keeps our body healthy and strong. **Yoga: Role of Education**

Yoga education can enhance all the activities of the students, be it academic or sport or social. Yoga techniques provide improved attention in studies, better stamina and co-ordination for sports and a heightened awareness and balanced attitude for social activity. Education in the largest sense is any act or experience that has a formative effect on the mind, character or physical ability of an individual. In its technical sense, education is the process by which society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another. Again, like most other practical areas of education, Yoga education imparts certain techniques and skills. Yoga education creates stress and on the other hand stress level can be reduced with their help of Yoga education. Research studies have shown improvement in spatial memory following Yoga breathing through a particular nostril in school children. The influence of Yoga on the development of memory needs to be

established through systematic and extensive scientific research. The nasal cycle is an ultrafine rhythm characterized by alternating patience of the left and right nostrils with periodicity of 1 to 8 hours.

Yoga (Sanskrit, Pāli) refers to traditional physical and mental disciplines originating in India. The word is associated with meditative practices in Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism.

Yoga Exercises

To maintain the purity of blood and elimination of toxins, both outer and inner cleanliness is indispensable. Scientists prescribe sun-bath, steam-bath, shower-bath, air-bath and to this the yogis include the nasal cleansing (neti), stomach wash (dhouti), the depuration of the alimentary canal (basti), the purgation of the intestines, the bladder, and the sexual organs (vajroli). Yoga exercises have a strengthening effect on the nervous system through its non-tiring physiological activities that bring about poise of body and mind. Unlike the normal workouts that concentrate more on the inflation of the muscles, Yoga takes care of every little part of the anatomy.

Yoga is much more than "a new-found ability to touch your toes." Asanas have an all-pervading effect on the physical and mental functioning of the body:

Physical - Through healing, strengthening, stretching and relaxing the skeletal, muscular, digestive, cardio-vascular, glandular and nervous systems.

Mental - Through the cultivation of a quite and a peaceful mind, alertness and concentration.

Spiritual - By preparing for meditation.

The physical discipline of Yoga involves specific breathing techniques and postures, called asanas - a Sanskrit term, which means "to sit in a particular position." In other words, asanas are the various positions that make up the practice of Yoga.

postures, sometimes combined with therapeutic verbal dialogue.

Physical Health Benefits

- a) Yoga improves strength, balance and flexibility. Slow movements and deep breathing increase blood flow and warm up muscles, while holding a pose can build strength.
- b) Yoga helps with back pain relief. Yoga is as good as basic stretching for easing pain and improving mobility in people with lower back pain. The American College of Physicians recommends yoga as a first-line treatment for chronic low back pain.
- c) Yoga can ease arthritis symptoms. Gentle yoga has been shown to ease some of the discomfort of tender, swollen joints for people with arthritis.

- d) Regular yoga practice can lower blood pressure, pulse rate, BMI, cholesterol levels, and circulatory strain. Yoga also improves vascular well-being by diminishing changes in the veins that add to coronary illness.
- e) Reduces Chronic Pain - Several researches and studies suggest that practising yoga can help reduce many types of chronic pain in conditions like carpal tunnel syndrome and osteoarthritis. Yoga is claimed to be better than exercise-based recuperation for lower back pains, as well.
- f) Improves Flexibility and Balance - Through the use of specific asanas or poses yoga can help increase the flexibility of your body. Regular yoga practice helps improve balance and mobility in older individuals.
- g) Increases muscle strength - Yoga is an excellent addition to your exercise routine for its strength-building benefits. There are specific poses or asanas in yoga that are designed to increase strength and build muscle. By practising yoga regularly, you can experience a significant increase in upper body strength and endurance. It also aids in weight loss and decreases body fat percentage.
- h) Improves respiration - Yogic breathing, also known as Pranayama, is a practice that focuses on controlling your breathing through various breathing exercises and techniques. It helps increase the vital capacity of the lungs and keeps asthma and other lung diseases at bay.

Mental Health Benefits

- a) Reduces stress - If you are wondering how to reduce stress, yoga is the answer. It is a well-known fact that yoga promotes relaxation, and hence you can turn to yoga for stress relief. Once you start practising yoga regularly, you can find a significant decrease in the secretion of cortisol, the primary hormone responsible for stress. It leads to an improved quality of life and mental health.
- b) Relieves anxiety - Many people feel on edge every now and then. Yoga can help you cope with feelings of anxiety and fear. Yoga is also proven to help reduce anxiety and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD).
- c) Fights depression - Yoga is an effective treatment for depression. Several studies have found that it acts as an anti-depressant due to its ability to decrease levels of cortisol, the stress hormone.

- d) Promotes sleep quality - Incorporating yoga into your daily routine will enhance your sleep quality as it increases the secretion of melatonin, a hormone responsible for regulating sleep and wakefulness. As a result, you will fall asleep faster, sleep for longer and feel well-rested in the morning.
- e) Stimulates brain function - As per a few studies, regular yoga practice can improve your mind's capacity and lift vitality levels. It also enhances the speed and precision of working memory, mental adaptability, task exchanging, and data review capabilities.

Importance of Yoga for students

There are six fundamentals' elements of Yoga. They are:

- a) Living Together (Yama): It promotes living in peace, observing moral rules and learning to live as part of a group.
- b) Cleaning Body and Mind (Niyama): It aims to eliminate toxins and negativity by maintaining the health of the body and mind.
- c) Straightening the Spine (Asana): It emphasises the importance of correct posture to prevent back pain, to discover our bodies and control movements effectively.
- d) Breathing (Pranayama): It helps in controlling the breath that can lead to purification, inner confidence, and an enhanced ability to resolve conflicts and monitor aggression.
- e) Relaxation (Pratyahara): It focuses on learning to relax. Periods of silence and structured rest are deemed essential in order to revitalise a person, and plant the seeds of calmness and confidence.
- f) Concentration (Dharana): It helps in heightening concentration and learning abilities. With its help, visual memory and other senses are developed, which enhance mental capacity to enrich thinking, understanding and imagining.

In the age of immense competition, yoga certainly holds the power to calm a racing mind. With the help of yoga, students can understand their capabilities and can widen their mental horizon. Yoga education could help to equip oneself with basic knowledge about one's personality, to learn to handle oneself well in all life situations, to learn techniques of gaining good health, to develop a discriminative mind capable of knowing the real from the unreal and to face the dualities of life with equanimity. Yoga education can enhance all the activities of the students, be it academic or sport or social. Proper exercise, proper breathing, proper relaxation, proper diet, and positive thinking are the five points that can help you reap the

benefits of Yoga to the fullest. Yoga techniques provide improved attention in studies, better stamina and co-ordination for sports and a heightened awareness and balanced attitude for social activity.

Conclusion

Yoga offers new learning possibilities to a wider group of students than traditional sports or fitness curriculum, making it a valuable addition to any educational program. Additionally, adding yoga to a school's curriculum will help provide a quality physical education program as modification of traditional physical education yoga in sports as important as other think it helps us in different ways and different levels in a sports men life. Yoga can play a key role in cultivating mind control and concentration which helps a sportsperson to perform at their game. It offers children and adults an opportunity to experience success in physical activity, which can help build a foundation of strong of life. Yoga exercises have a strengthening effect on the nervous system through its non-tiring physiological activities that bring about poise of body and mind. Unlike the normal workouts that concentrate more on the inflation of the muscles, Yoga takes care of every little part of the anatomy. Again, like most other practical areas of education, Yoga education imparts certain techniques and skills. Just as we might show someone how to solder a joint in water pipes, we might show someone how to perform a Yoga asana or pranayama. Yoga requires active participation of the subject by synchronizing physical movements with changes at the mental level. This becomes interesting with the possibility of Yoga training or drill in schools and colleges.

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